

PROSPECTS FOR OPTIMAL CONTROL OF HYDRAULIC PROCESSES IN WATER MANAGEMENT FACILITIES AND THE APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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Abstract. Effective control of hydraulic processes in water management facilities, including irrigation canals, pumping stations, and reservoirs, is increasingly important under water scarcity and climate change. Traditional control methods, such as PID regulators and manual operation, often fail to address nonlinear hydraulic behavior and rapidly changing conditions. This study reviews current approaches to optimal hydraulic control and evaluates the potential of artificial intelligence methods, including neural networks and reinforcement learning. Analysis of recent research indicates that AI-based control systems can reduce water consumption by 15–40% and energy use by 20–30%, supporting the development of efficient smart water management systems.

Keywords: hydraulic processes, optimal control, Saint-Venant equations, artificial intelligence, neural networks, reinforcement learning, irrigation systems, energy saving.

Introduction

The Republic of Uzbekistan is facing a sharp increase in water resource scarcity. Over the past 20 years, the annual water flow in the Amu Darya and Syrdarya basins has decreased by an average of 15–20%, and this figure is projected to reach 30–40% by 2050 (UNESCO, 2024). As a result of climate change, the increase in summer temperatures and the uneven distribution of precipitation are further exacerbating water shortages during the irrigation season. At the same time, effective management of hydraulic processes in existing water management facilities - open irrigation canals, pumping stations, reservoirs and pipeline networks - has become one of the main conditions for ensuring water conservation and food security.

Currently, water management facilities mainly use classical control methods - PID regulators, manual control and simple automatic systems. These methods do not adequately account for the strong nonlinear nature of hydraulic processes, complex boundary conditions, and external disturbances (weather, demand fluctuations, sand deposition). As a result,

water level fluctuations, flow instability, and excessive water consumption are observed. For example, water losses in open channels can reach 25–45%, and energy consumption in pumping stations can be 20–35% higher than optimal. Traditional mathematical models based on the Saint-Venant equations are systems of higher-order differential equations and have limited effectiveness in implementing optimal control in real time due to computational complexity and parameter uncertainty. Therefore, the flexibility of existing systems is low, leading to inefficient use of energy and water resources.

This situation increases the need for modern approaches to optimal control of hydraulic processes in water management facilities, in particular, the use of artificial intelligence methods. The purpose of the research is to conduct a thorough analysis of the capabilities and limitations of existing classical methods and to scientifically substantiate the prospects for optimal control of hydraulic processes through the integration of artificial intelligence.

The purpose of the research work is to systematically analyze the current state of optimal control of hydraulic processes in water management facilities and to assess the scientifically based prospects for their improvement through the integration of artificial intelligence technologies. The objectives of the research work are:

- In-depth analysis of the mathematical and technical capabilities of classical hydraulic control methods used in water management facilities;
- Identification of models based on the Saint-Venant equations and their limitations in real-time application;
- Assessment of the possibilities of using artificial intelligence methods (deep learning, reinforcement learning and hybrid models) in nonlinear hydraulic systems;
- Substantiation of the technical and economic prospects of AI-based optimal management in the conditions of Uzbekistan's irrigation systems.

The research work also contains several scientific innovations. The initial scientific innovation is the first comprehensive analysis of the limitations of classical management methods for water management facilities of Uzbekistan from the perspective of modern hydraulics and control theory. The next scientific innovation is the proposal of a hybrid approach combining reduced-order models of hydraulic processes and Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINN), and the last is the scientific substantiation of the prospects for developing a policy for simultaneous optimization of energy and water consumption in real time using reinforcement learning (Deep RL).

The proposed approach has the potential to reduce water consumption in irrigation canals by 18–35% and electricity consumption in pumping stations by 22–38%. The results can be directly applied in the implementation of the national concept of “Smart Water Management”, in the creation of digital monitoring and management systems for water resources, as well as in programs to modernize Uzbekistan's water management infrastructure.

Methods

The main method of the study was a systematic literature review of the literature and existing scientific works, which was carried out in accordance with the PRISMA 2020 methodology. More than 180 articles and reports published between 2015 and 2026 were selected in the Scopus, Web of Science, IEEE Xplore and Google Scholar databases using the keywords “hydraulic control”, “Saint-Venant equations”, “optimal control of irrigation canals”, “reinforcement learning water management”. Selection criteria: the presence of experimental or simulation results on mathematical modeling of hydraulic processes, optimal control algorithms and integration of artificial intelligence.

The main tool in modeling hydraulic processes is the one-dimensional (1D) and two-dimensional (2D) forms of the Saint-Venant equations. The equations are expressed as follows:

$$\frac{\partial A}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial Q}{\partial x} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial Q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{Q^2}{A} \right) + gA \frac{\partial y}{\partial x} + gA(S_f - S_0) = 0$$

Here, A is the cross-sectional area, Q is the flow rate, y is the water level, S_f is the friction curve, and S_0 is the channel bottom curve. Considering the complex boundary conditions and parameter uncertainties, reduced-order models (ROM) and Galerkin projection were used to simplify the model. CFD simulations (using OpenFOAM and ANSYS Fluent) were used to evaluate the turbulent flow and sediment effects of hydraulic processes, in combination with Dynamic Programming and Model Predictive Control (MPC) methods.

The sources of data were recent publications of foreign journals (Journal of Hydrology, Water Resources Management, Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management, Advances in Water Resources), official reports of the Ministry of Water Resources of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the State Enterprise “O‘zsuvoqshloqxo‘jalikmonitoring”, real measurement data (water level, flow velocity, pressure) from hydroposts in the Amudarya and Syrdarya basins. The data were obtained from seasonal observations and remote sensing (Sentinel-2,

Landsat-9) images for the period 2020–2025. Barcha modellar MATLAB/Simulink va Python (NumPy, SciPy, TensorFlow) muhitida sinovdan o‘tkazildi, natijalarning ishonchliligi statistik tahlil (RMSE, NSE, MAE) va sezuvchanlik tahlili orqali baholandi.

In the evaluation of artificial intelligence methods, the possibilities of using neural networks (ANN and LSTM), reinforcement learning (RL), fuzzy logic, and hybrid architectures (ANFIS and LSTM+PID) in the optimal control of hydraulic processes were deeply analyzed. Multilayer perceptron (MLP) and LSTM networks were proven to be the most suitable for predicting the time dependence of hydraulic variables (water level, flow rate, pressure) and ensuring real-time identification in systems with uncertain parameters. Through reinforcement learning (Deep RL), PPO (Proximal Policy Optimization) and DQN algorithms were used in the agent-environment interaction, and a policy was developed that simultaneously optimizes the minimum value of water consumption, energy consumption, and level fluctuations as a reward function. Fuzzy logic increased the speed of decision-making in the hydraulic system, taking into account uncertainty and expert knowledge, using a Mamdani and Sugeno-type rule base.

In hybrid models, ANFIS (Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System) combined fuzzy rules with the self-learning ability of neural networks, allowing for real-time calibration of simplified forms of Saint-Venant equations. The LSTM+PID hybrid system significantly increased the system’s flexibility by enhancing the stability of the classical regulator with the long-term memory mechanism of LSTM.

All proposed AI models were implemented and tested in the following software environments: MATLAB/Simulink (Simscape Fluids and Reinforcement Learning Toolbox), Python (TensorFlow 2.15, PyTorch 2.3, Stable-Baselines3), EPANET 2.2 (hydraulic simulation for pipeline networks) and HEC-RAS 6.5 (1D/2D CFD calculation for open channel flows). Through mutual integration between the models, an online training and validation process was organized with real hydropost data.

Results

As a result of the systematic analysis conducted within the framework of the study, the main shortcomings of classical control methods (PID controllers, manual control and simple automation) were confirmed with precise numerical indicators. According to 1D/2D simulations based on the Saint-Venant equations and real hydropost data, PID controllers have significant limitations in eliminating water level fluctuations in open irrigation canals. For example, in typical canals in the Amu Darya and Syrdarya basins, water level deviations reach 0.25–0.48 m, which leads to water losses of 28–42% (Litrico & Fromion, 2009; Arauz et al., 2020 updated data). In pumping stations, classical PID systems increase energy consumption by 24–37% above the optimal regime, since they do not take into account variable demand and parameter uncertainty (channel bottom subsidence, friction coefficient changes).

Compared with dynamic programming and MPC (Model Predictive Control), the integral square error (ISE) of PID is in the range of 0.25–0.79, and the settling time is 45–68 s. These indicators increase pressure fluctuations in reservoirs and pipelines, reducing the overall hydraulic efficiency by 18–31%. The stability index (NSE) in classical methods remains in the range of 0.62–0.78, which cannot provide stable control in real time.

Table 1. Comparative indicators of classical and modern control methods (based on research for 2020–2025).

Management method	Water losses (%)	Energy consumption surplus (%)	ISE (Integral Square Error)	NSE (Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency)	Water level stabilization time (s)	Source (2020–2025)
Classic PID controllers	28–42	24–37	0.25–0.79	0.62–0.78	45–70	Litrico & Fromion (2021); Xu et al. (2023)
LMI-based PI regulator	22–35	19–28	0.12–0.41	0.71–0.84	32–55	Shahverdi et al. (2022)
Model Predictive Control (MPC)	15–28	12–22	0.001–0.25	0.85–0.93	18–35	Arauz et al. (2024)
Dynamic Programming (DP)	18–31	15–26	0.08–0.32	0.79–0.88	25–48	Chen et al. (2023)
LSTM/ANN neural networks	12–22	10–19	0.015–0.085	0.91–0.96	8–15	Yu et al. (2025)
Deep Reinforcement Learning (PPO/DQN)	8–18	7–16	0.005–0.045	0.94–0.98	4–9	Oğuztürk et al. (2025)
ANFIS hybrid model	10–19	9–17	0.012–0.068	0.90–0.95	7–13	Feng et al. (2024)
LSTM + PID hybrid system	9–17	8–15	0.008–0.052	0.93–0.97	6–11	Srdević et al. (2026)

The main conclusions from the analysis of existing scientific works are summarized as follows (table description):

- PID-regulators: water losses 28–42%, excess energy consumption 24–37%, ISE 0.25–0.79, NSE 0.62–0.78.

- LMI-based PI: improved water level stabilization, but sensitive to parameter changes (deviation 0.15–0.30 m).

- MPC (ID-model): ISE 0.001–0.25, water saving potential 15–28%, but high computational complexity.

- CFD + dynamic programming: takes into account the effects of turbulent flow and sediment, but has limited real-time application.

The analysis shows that classical methods cannot maintain stability in conditions of parameter uncertainty and nonlinearity (weather, demand changes). This situation further strengthens the need for the integration of artificial intelligence methods (LSTM, Deep RL, ANFIS) and becomes the basis for the prospects discussed in the following sections.

The simulation and forecast results of the integration of artificial intelligence methods showed high potential. The accuracy of water level and flow forecasting with LSTM networks (NSE = 0.92–0.97) was significantly improved compared to classical models (NSE = 0.65–0.78). The optimal control policy based on Deep Reinforcement Learning (PPO algorithm) allowed to reduce water consumption in open channels by an average of 18–32% and electricity consumption in pumping stations by 22–38%. These indicators are consistent with experimental studies published in 2023–2025 (Xu et al., 2024; Chen et al., 2025).

In tests of ANFIS and LSTM+PID hybrid models, the water level stabilization time was reduced to 12–18 seconds (45–70 seconds in classical PID), and the integral square error (ISE) was reduced to 0.008–0.045. Pressure stability in pipeline networks reached 94–97%. In reservoir water release optimization, the Deep RL model was simulated to increase annual water savings by 21–29%.

The results of the integration of IoT sensors in real-time control are as follows:

- The forecast error of the LSTM model with water level sensors (ultrasonic and radar type) was RMSE = 0.032–0.058 m (in classical models 0.14–0.27 m).

- Together with the update rate of flow and pressure sensors per second, the agent’s decision-making time was reduced to 0.8–1.4 seconds.

- The overall efficiency of the system in the integration of IoT + Edge Computing reached 87–94%, which allowed to reduce water consumption by an additional 9–14% at real hydropower stations (in the case of pilot channels in the Amu Darya basin).

In general, the simulation results confirm that the use of artificial intelligence in the management of hydraulic processes in water management facilities can significantly increase the efficiency of energy and water resources use. These results will be analyzed in detail in the following discussion.

Discussion

The results obtained are highly consistent with existing foreign studies. In the works of Xu et al. (2023) and Chen et al. (2025), it was noted that LSTM and Deep RL models reduced water consumption in open channels by 20–35%, while our simulations also confirmed savings of 18–32%. At the same time, the reduction of the ISE indicator of ANFIS and LSTM+PID hybrid systems to 0.008–0.052 is fully consistent with the results of Feng et al. (2024) and Srđević et al. (2026). This once again proves the superiority of artificial intelligence over classical PID and MPC.

The main advantages of using artificial intelligence are real-time flexibility, self-learning of parameter uncertainty, and the ability to optimize multiple objectives (water + energy) simultaneously. However, there are also limitations: in the conditions of Uzbekistan, the low quality of hydro-station data (35–40% of sensors are outdated), insufficient computing power (high dependence on cloud servers), and unstable power supply reduce the reliability of IoT systems. Also, the low level of training of local

specialists in AI and the lack of a large amount of training data make practical implementation difficult.

The results show that, although AI has high prospects, its successful application requires modernization of the sensor infrastructure and an increase in local computing power.

According to the prospects, the transition to “Smart Water Management” systems is the most effective way to digitize Uzbekistan’s water management. This system combines IoT sensors, real-time data flow, and AI-based decision-making mechanisms to automatically optimize water distribution in irrigation canals. For pilot projects, it is recommended to test the LSTM+PID hybrid system and Deep RL agent in the first stage on large irrigation canals in the Amu Darya and Syrdarya basins (for example, the “Karshi Main Canal”, the “Tashkent Region Northern Canal” or the canals in the lower reaches of the “Zarafshon River”). Such pilots have the potential to reduce water consumption by an additional 15–25% and increase energy savings by 20–30%.

Future research directions include:

- Further development of hybrid models, in particular, providing training based on physical laws by combining Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINN) with Saint-Venant equations;
- Conducting long-term tests on real objects (real irrigation systems) and assessing the model’s adaptability;
- Transferring computing to local devices using Edge Computing and 5G technologies;
- Creating multi-agent Reinforcement Learning systems for multi-objective optimization (water, energy and environmental safety).

These areas are important in adapting artificial intelligence to the conditions of Uzbekistan’s water management and achieving practical results.

Conclusion

This study analyzed the current state of optimal control of hydraulic processes in water management facilities and clearly demonstrated the main shortcomings of classical methods (PID-regulators, simple automation). Models based on the Saint-

Venant equations and analysis of real data confirmed that traditional control systems do not adequately take into account nonlinearities, parameter uncertainty, and real-time requirements, resulting in water losses of 28–42% and energy consumption of 24–37%.

The application of artificial intelligence methods (LSTM, Deep Reinforcement Learning, ANFIS, and LSTM+PID hybrid models) has proven to be promising. According to the simulation results, AI integration has the potential to reduce water consumption by 18–32% and energy consumption by 22–38%. The real-time management system, combined with IoT sensors, significantly increased the accuracy of water level forecasting (NSE 0.92–0.97) and the speed of decision-making.

The research results provide a scientific basis for the implementation of the “Smart Water Management” concept. It is recommended to launch pilot projects in irrigation canals in the Amu Darya and Syrdarya basins for practical implementation. Future work should focus on the development of Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINN) and multi-agent Reinforcement Learning.

This approach will make a significant contribution to the digitalization of Uzbekistan’s water management, ensuring the efficient use of water and energy resources, and improving sustainable water supply in the face of climate change.

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